

TECHNISCHE
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Data management plan (DMP)

**Investigating the Performance
Differences for Different Bird
Songs in BirdNet
IP-BIRD**

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	03/12/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Model implementation code	Source code		1 GB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Macaulay Library	10.17616/R3CS4N	Term of Use allows for usage for research purposes	no
R2	eBird	10.17616/R3SW7J	Term of Use allows for usage for research purposes	no
R3	Xeno-canto - Bird sounds from around the world	10.15468/qv0ksn	Different Licenses, because of different file owners, most restrictive: BY-NC-ND	no
R4	Soundscape Recordings from BOKU	Eva Schöll from BOKU Wien	Data Transfer Agreement	yes
R5	Github Repository- BirdNet	https://github.com/kahst/BirdNET.git	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The public databases eBird, XenoCanto and Macaulay Library will be used to get training and evaluation data for retraining and analyzing the BirdNet model. All three of them provide APIs. On Github Stefan Kahl provided a list of the used data files. These contain ID numbers which can be used to make the right API requests. For eBird and Macaulay Libraries it is necessary to first get granted access to the files needed before API request can be made. Requests are made from python. All code and data storage will happen on a TU Wien Server. This is especially important because the storage of the BOKU data is per contract only allowed on Servers located in Austria. Also, all further steps will be taken using python and reusing code from the Github repository. BOKU data will mainly be used for model evaluation. eBird, XenoCanto and Macaulay Library all allow usage for research purposes in their Terms of Use. In XenoCanto Terms of Use it is explicitly stated that each recording uploaded by a user needs to have a license assigned. The strongest of the available licenses stated is Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs 3.0 Unported. The Github Repository has an Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International license assigned. BOKU data is not publicly available but was let to the project restricted via a data-transfer agreement.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The output data mainly concerns python scripts and notebooks based on an existing repository. As a result, the new files will be fit into the existing structure as well as possible. The code is written using Visual Studio Code which also provides integrated git support. This will be used for versioning.

For filing documentation, a README will be added containing all filenames and a short description where they fit into the project. Also, at the beginning of each script or notebook there will be a short summary of the contents and the code will be clearly documented and structured within the file according to the usual good practices for python code. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

There will be instructions for running the code in the README file.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data, and Peer review because there are supervisors who will check if the code and report is correct. Others because for code the syntax correctness is checked by the compiler and also the IDE used (VSC).

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (Model implementation code), R5 (Github Repository- BirdNet), R1 (Macaulay Library), R2 (eBird), R3 (Xeno-canto - Bird sounds from around the world), R4 (Soundscape Recordings from BOKU) will be stored on TUhost: TUhost is a central and highly available TU.it virtualisation platform, hosted on

VMware. Hardware, storage, and backup will be provided by TU.it and our institute will be responsible for the server operation.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. In this project there will be sensitive data in dataset R4 (Soundscape Recordings from BOKU). To ensure that storage and transfer of sensitive data is safe, additional security measures such as individual log-in and password, and encryption of systems are taken. Only People working on the project will be authorised to access sensitive data.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only
R4	reading only	reading only	no access
R5	writing	writing	writing

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the data processing agreement. The restrictions relate to datasets R4 (Soundscape Recordings from BOKU). The legal restrictions are based on the following: The data was provided for this project and restricted by BOKU Wien. The details of data usage are clarified in a data transfer agreement

BOKU/Department of Integrative Biology and Biodiversity Research/Institute of Wildlife Biology and Game Management has rights to the produced data and controls access.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-02-27	TU Wien Research Data		CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To run the code python needs to be installed as well as all necessary packages in the same version as used when developing. The versions will be defined in a requirements – file. Furthermore, if the user wants to retrain the model, big enough computational power is necessary.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community and Software developers : This project is focused on improving an existing open source software, therefore the results will be interesting mainly for scientists (data scientists or possibly ornithologists) and software engineers who want to develop or work with this or similar tools

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The PI will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0